

A Flavonol-diglycoside from *Melastoma melabathricum*

B. DINDA* and M. K. SAHA

Department of Chemistry, Tripura University, Agartala-799 004

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A new flavonol-diglycoside was isolated from the methanolic extract of the aerial parts of *Melastoma melabathricum*. Its structure was established as quercetin-3-O- α -L-rhamnosyl-(1 \rightarrow 2)- β -D-galactoside on the basis of physical and chemical evidences.

THE family, *Melastomataceae* comprises¹ of 240 genera and 3000 species in tropical and subtropical regions. Only 4 genera, namely *Melastoma*, *Osbeckia*, *Somerila* and *Memecylon* are found in Tripura. The species, *Melastoma melabathricum* Linn., an endemic shrub of Tripura, possesses medicinal properties². Earlier communications on this plant reported³⁻⁵ a number of compounds. In continuation of our studies, we present here the isolation and structure determination of a new flavonol-diglycoside.

Results and Discussion

The glycoside (1), m.p. 214°, $[\alpha]_D - 8.4^\circ$ (MeOH), was obtained as a brownish solid from the BuOH layer of the MeOH extract of the defatted aerial parts of the plant. The chromatographic data (see Experimental), colour reaction (dull ochre to yellow in uv + NH₃) and λ_{max} (MeOH) 259 (log ϵ , 4.10), 265sh (3.64), 295sh (3.44), and 360 (3.97); (+NaOMe) 272 (3.33), 328 (3.12) and 410 (3.24); (+NaOAc) 274 (3.70), 325sh (3.40) and 387 (3.72); (+NaOAc + H₃BO₃) 262 (3.77), 300sh (3.40) and 377 (3.60); (+AlCl₃) 274 (3.68), 302sh (3.30), 332sh (3.40) and 435 (3.78); (+AlCl₃ + HCl) 269 (3.6), 300sh (3.31), 364sh (3.43) and 402 (4.60) were diagnostic^{6,7} of flavonol-3-O-glycosides with oxygen functions at C-5, C-7, C-3' and C-4'. The presence of glycosidic linkage was indicated by a band at 1110–1010 cm⁻¹ in its ir spectra. The CI-mass spectra (CH₄ as reactant gas) of the glycoside showed aglycone ion at m/z 303 [M+H]⁺ and sugar fragmentation ions at m/z 325 [1 hexose + 1 deoxyhexose - 2H₂O + CH₃]⁺, 179 [hexosyl + CH₃]⁺, 163 [deoxyhexosyl + CH₃]⁺, 147, 146 [deoxyhexosyl]⁺, 145 and 129 (147 - H₂O)⁺, suggesting (Scheme 1) it to be a quercetin deoxyhexosyl hexoside. Its 100 MHz ¹H nmr spectra (CD₃OD) signals at δ 1.26 (3H, d, J 7.0 Hz, deoxyhexosyl-Me), 3.30–3.70 (m, sugar-H), 4.86 (1H, inf. in peak of HDO, may be deoxyhexosyl-1''), 5.30 (1H, d, J 7.0 Hz, hexosyl H-1''), 6.20 (1H, d, J 2.5 Hz, H-6) 6.38 (1H, d, J 2.5 Hz, H-8), 6.84 (1H, d, J 8.5 Hz, H-5'), 7.50 (1H, d, J 2.5 Hz, H-2') and 7.70 (1H, q, J 2.5 Hz and 8.5 Hz, H-6') reveal^{6,7,9,10} the glycoside to be quercetin-3-O-deoxyhexosyl-hexo-

side. The position of anomeric proton signal of deoxyhexose of the glycoside was clearly observed in the ¹H nmr spectra (100 MHz) of its TMS derivative in CCl₄ at δ 4.90 (1H, d, J 2.0 Hz), which suggested⁸ the inter-glycosidic linkage to be (1 \rightarrow 2).

Total acid hydrolysis of the glycoside with aqueous 2N HCl afforded quercetin (2) and equimolar amounts of D-galactose and L-rhamnose. Therefore, the hexose is assigned as galactose and deoxyhexose as rhamnose in the glycoside. Mild acid hydrolysis of the glycoside with formic acid in cyclohexanol¹¹ gave quercetin-3-O-galactoside confirming the direct attachment of the galactose to the aglycone. Kuhn methylation¹² of the glycoside with MeI in DMF in presence of Ag₂O followed by acid hydrolysis with 2N HCl afforded an aglycone, identified as quercetin-3',4',5,7-tetra-methyl ether and two sugars, identified¹³ as 3,4,6-tri-O-methyl-D-galactose and 2,3,4-tri-O-methyl-L-rhamnose. Thus, the inter-glycosidic linkage is confirmed as (1 \rightarrow 2). The coupling constants $J_{H-1''-H-2''(a,b)}$ 7.0 Hz and $J_{H-1''-H-2''(e,a)}$ 2.0 Hz suggest that galactose is β -linked and rhamnose α -linked in the glycoside. Therefore, the glycoside is assigned as quercetin-3-O- α -L-rhamnosyl-(1 \rightarrow 2)- β -D-galactoside (1). To the best of our knowledge, the compound is new. The inter-glycosidic linkage (1 \rightarrow 2) in rhamnogalactose was reported¹⁴ earlier in the characterisation of kaemferol-3-O-rhamnosyl-(1 \rightarrow 2)-galactoside, isolated from *Chenopodium fremontii* (*Chenopodiaceae*) leaf.

Experimental

Melting points were determined on a Köfeler block and is uncorrected. Silica gel (60–120 mesh) was used for column chromatography and silica gel G for tlc. Uv spectra were measured in aldehyde-free MeOH and ir spectra in KBr. Whatman No. 1 was used for paper chromatography and Whatman 3 mm paper for paper electrophoresis and preparative paper chromatography.

Aerial parts of the plant¹⁵ were collected from the tilla areas of Agartala in May 1985. The plant material was air-dried prior to extraction.

Scheme 1

Isolation of the glycoside (1): Ground plant material (6.0 kg) was extracted with petrol (b.p. 60–80°) for 48 h and the defatted material was extracted with commercial MeOH (90%) for 48 h. The MeOH extract was concentrated under reduced pressure until only H₂O remained. The aqueous layer was extracted successively with EtOAc and n-BuOH. The BuOH layer was concentrated and column-chromatographed. The column was eluted with C₆H₆, C₆H₆-EtOAc (9 : 1, 6 : 1, 3 : 1, 1 : 1), EtOAc, EtOAc-MeOH (9 : 1, 6 : 1, 3 : 1, 1 : 1) and finally with MeOH. The EtOAc-MeOH (9 : 1) eluate on evaporation of solvent gave a brown solid, which was found to be a mixture of two components on tlc. The solid was further column-chromatographed, when the glycoside (0.096 g) was obtained from EtOAc-MeOH (5 : 1) eluate; a single component on tlc: R_f, 0.30 in EtOAc-C₆H₆-MeOH (3 : 1 : 1) and pc: R_f, 0.47 in n-BuOH-HOAc-H₂O (4 : 1 : 5, upper phase), 0.40 in H₂O, 0.44 in PhOH satd. with H₂O and 0.52 in 15% HOAc (Found: C, 52.82; H, 4.41. C₂₇H₃₀O₁₆ requires C, 53.01; H, 4.95%); ν_{max} 3 400 (OH), 1 645 (chelated conjugated C=O), 1 605 (C=C) and 1 110–1 010 cm⁻¹ (glycosidic linkage); CI-MS m/z (abundance %) 325 (62.5), 303 (100.0), 179 (11.5), 163 (32.2), 147 (27.2), 146 (18.5), 145 (25.4) and 129 (29.5).

Trimethylsilylation of the glycoside (1): The glycoside (0.008 g) was dissolved in anhydrous pyridine (4 drops), and each of hexamethyldisilazane (5 drops) and trimethylchlorosilane (5 drops) were subsequently added to it. The solution was kept for 10 min at room temperature and the solvent and excess reagent were removed under reduced pressure and the residue was dissolved in spectral CCl₄ for ¹H nmr analysis, δ (100 MHz) 1.26 (3H, d, J 7.0 Hz, rhamnose Me), 3.30–3.65 (m, sugar-H), 4.90 (1H, d, J 2.6 Hz, rhamnosyl H-1'''), 5.30 (1H, d, J 7.0 Hz, galactosyl H-1''), 6.20 (1H, d, J 2.5 Hz, H-6), 6.40 (1H, d, J 2.5 Hz, H-8), 6.84 (1H, d, J 8.5 Hz, H-5'), 7.52 (1H, d, J 2.5 Hz, H-2') and 7.70 (1H, q, J 2.5 Hz and 8.5 Hz, H-6').

Total acid hydrolysis of 1 : 1 (0.03 g) was refluxed with 2N HCl (10 ml) in EtOH (1 : 1) at 100° for 4 h. The reaction mixture was concentrated under reduced pressure. A little cold H₂O was added to the mixture and then it was extracted with EtOAc. The EtOAc layer was dried and the residue recrystallised from EtOH to get 2 (8 mg), m.p. 302°; λ_{max} (MeOH) 256, 269sh, 302sh and 370 nm; EI-MS m/z 302 [M]⁺ (100.0), 301 [M-1]⁺ (17.6), 285 [M-OH]⁺ (2.9), 284 [M-H₂O]⁺ (3.9), 273 [M-CO-H]⁺ (27.9), 257 [285-CO]⁺ (11.0), 229 [257-CO]⁺ (38.2), 153 [A+H]⁺ (41.2), 137 [B]⁺

(83.3), 124 [$A-CO$]⁺ (34.3), 109 [$B-CO$]⁺ (64.7) (Scheme 1; lit. data⁷) and co-tlc with an authentic sample confirmed it to be quercetin. The aqueous layer was neutralised with Ag_2CO_3 and filtered. The filtrate was concentrated under reduced pressure to a syrupy residue and it was identified as a mixture of D galactose and L-rhamnose by co-pc in n-BuOH- $C_6H_5N-H_2O$ (6:4:3); EtOAc-AcOH- H_2O (9:2:2); $CHCl_3-MeOH-H_2O$ (65:35:10, lower phase) and horizontal paper electrophoresis in boric acid-borax buffer¹⁶ at pH 9.2 with authentic samples.

Partial acid hydrolysis of 1 : 1 (0.02 g) was refluxed with formic acid (85%)-cyclohexanol (1:1; 10 ml) under stirring for 20 h and the reaction mixture was concentrated under reduced pressure, diluted with H_2O and extracted with EtOAc-n-BuOH (4:1). The organic layer was evaporated to a residue under reduced pressure. The residue was a mixture of three components which were separated by ppc in BAW.

The middle spot ($R_f=0.55$) was identified as quercetin-3-O-galactoside, λ_{max} (MeOH) 256, 269sh, 300sh and 362 nm (lit. data⁶). The aqueous layer was neutralised with Ag_2CO_3 and filtered. The filtrate was concentrated under reduced pressure to a syrup which was identified as L-rhamnose by co-pc with an authentic sample.

Acid hydrolysis of quercetin-3-O-galactoside : The above syrupy residue was refluxed with 2N HCl-EtOH (1:1; 8 ml) at 100° for 0.5 h. The reaction mixture was concentrated under reduced pressure and was worked up in the usual manner when quercetin (identified by co-tlc with an authentic sample) and galactose (identified by co-pc with an authentic sample) were found.

Hydrolysis of the permethylated product :

Permethylation of 1 : 1 (0.02 g) was dissolved in DMF (3 ml). Then MeI (5 ml) and Ag_2O (1 g) were added to it and the mixture was stirred for 18 h at room temperature. The reaction mixture was filtered and washed the residue with a little $CHCl_3$. The filtrate was concentrated under reduced pressure to a residue and it was refluxed with 10 ml of 2N HCl-EtOH (1:1; 10 ml) for 4 h. The reaction mixture was concentrated under reduced pressure and extracted with EtOAc. The EtOAc layer was evaporated to a solid residue, which was crystallised from Et_2O (5 mg), m.p. 194°; λ_{max} (MeOH) 253 (log ϵ , 3.75), 270sh (2.40), 302sh (2.04), 362 (3.63), (lit. data⁶); it was identified as quercetin-3',4',5',7-tetramethyl ether. The aqueous

layer was neutralised with Ag_2CO_3 and filtered. The filtrate was concentrated under reduced pressure to a residue (8 mg) which was identified as a mixture of 3,4,6-tri-O-methyl-D-galactose and 2,3,4-tri-O-methyl-L-rhamnose by co-tlc in $C_6H_6-MeCOMe$ (2:1) and co-pc in n-octane-isopropanol-aqueous 10% NH_4OH (50:25:2, v/v) and isooctane-isopropanol-aqueous 10% NH_4OH (65:25:2, v/v) with authentic samples.

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